

Co-digestion of harvested microalgae and primary sludge in a mesophilic anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR): methane potential and microbial diversity.

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ABSTRACT

Anaerobic co-digestion of primary sludge and raw microalgae (*Scenedesmus* and *Chlorella*) was performed in a lab-scale semi-continuous anaerobic membrane bioreactor to assess the biological performance and identify the microbial community involved in the co-digestion process. The reactor was operated at 35 °C for 440 days, working at a solids retention time of 100 days. The system achieved 73% biodegradability and showed high stability in terms of pH and volatile fatty acids. An enriched microbial community was observed. Of the several phyla, Chloroflexi and Proteobacteria were the most abundant. Cellulose-degraders phyla (Bacteroidetes, Chloroflexi and Thermotogae) were detected. Syntrophic microorganisms played an important role in intermediate degradation, enhancing methane production, mainly carried out by *Methanosaeta*. A nutrient-rich effluent (400 mg NH₄-N·L⁻¹ and 29 mg PO₄-P·L⁻¹) and digestate (860 mg N·L⁻¹ and 151 mg P·L⁻¹) were obtained. The bio-nutrients released from anaerobic co-digestion could be reused for microalgae cultivation or agricultural applications.

Keywords: co-digestion; AnMBR; microalgae; primary sludge; methane

1. INTRODUCTION

Expanding energy consumption due to industrialization and population growth has encouraged the scientific community to search for alternative renewable and eco-friendly energy sources to substitute fossil fuels. Thanks to its potential for nutrient removal or recovery from wastewater streams, microalgae cultivation has received increasing interest in recent years (Viruela et al., 2016) and has also attracted the attention of the bioenergy field. Microalgae are a valuable source of chemical products, including different types of biofuels and by-products. Algae yield about 20 times more than existing oilseed crops and could provide considerably more biodiesel than other crops while consuming less water and land and thus appear as a promising feedstock for the ideal third generation biofuel.

However, recent analyses have shown that algal biodiesel production requires further refinement to become economically viable, due to the high cost of lipid extraction (Acién et al., 2013). Anaerobic digestion (AD), which transforms biomass into biogas, is another alternative for recovering energy from algal biomass. Golueke et al. (1957) were the first to report on the AD of two microalgae genera: *Chlorella* and *Scenedesmus*. Sialve et al. (2009) found that AD is a suitable method of generating bioenergy from microalgae, while Zamalloa et al. (2012a) observed low conversion efficiency (30%) when digesting *Scenedesmus obliquus*. González-Fernández et al. (2013) reported a 9.4% biodegradability in a mesophilic continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR) for untreated *Scenedesmus* spp. Mahdy et al. (2014) found raw *Chlorella vulgaris* to be more biodegradable (50%) than the results of other earlier studies (Mendez et al., 2013). *Scenedesmus* and *Chlorella* have similar rigid cellulose-based cell wall that hampers their degradation, although differences in AD have been observed between these two species. Mussnug et al. (2010) reported lower methane

production when digesting *Scenedesmus* than with *Chlorella* while, Frigon et al. (2013) found *Scenedesmus* to give the highest methane yield.

During anaerobic digestion, the initial organic phosphorus and nitrogen biomass constituents are converted into phosphate and ammonium, which can be recycled for different uses such as microalgae cultivation, reducing the costs associated with commercial fertilizers (Christenson et al., 2011). Nutrient-loaded effluent from an anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) has been shown to be a suitable substrate for microalgae cultivation (Viruela et al., 2016). Greses et al. (2018) reported that anaerobic digestion of *Scenedesmus* from AnMBR effluent reached $146 \text{ mL CH}_4 \cdot \text{g COD}_{\text{inf}}^{-1}$, working at the low solids retention time (SRT) of 35 d under mesophilic conditions in an AnMBR. This wastewater treatment scheme appears to be a promising approach for circular economy models, since energy, nutrients and reclaimed water are recovered (Seco et al., 2018).

However, a few studies have indicated that biogas production during anaerobic digestion is limited owing to the algal sludge resisting biodegradation (Carrere et al., 2016). In addition, the high protein content yields a low C/N ratio (typically below 10), which could disturb long-term anaerobic mono-digestion (Saratale et al., 2018). The lower the C/N, the higher the concentration of the free ammonia nitrogen (FAN) released, which is an important intermediate product that can unsettle and possibly inhibit the process due to the accumulation of volatile fatty acids (VFA) and lower pH.

One alternative to improve microalgae digestibility is co-digestion with other carbon-rich substrates, such as waste paper, food waste and primary and secondary sludge. Compared with other ways of improving microalgae biodegradability, such as the use of pre-treatments, these carbon-rich co-substrates increase the C/N ratio, improving

process stability, increasing efficiency and reducing operating costs. Previous studies have demonstrated the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of anaerobic co-digestion (ACoD) to avoid ammonia inhibition (Saratale et al., 2018; Sialve et al., 2009).

Additional studies based on batch tests (Olsson et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2013) have shown that sewage sludge is a suitable feedstock for ACoD with microalgae.

Particularly, due to its high lipid content (Solé-Bundó et al., 2019), primary sludge shows promise as a co-substrate for enhancing microalgae biodegradability through ACoD, while this strategy of combining primary sludge and microalgae co-digestion would optimize the management of sludge streams in future water resource recovery facilities.

Since AD involves a complex network of metabolic interactions between different microorganisms, analysing the composition of microbial communities can help us to understand microalgae co-digestion. For instance, the acclimation capacity of different inocula for degrading microalgae without any pre-treatment (Gonzalez-Fernandez et al., 2018) is an effective strategy. According to 16S rRNA gene analysis, this capacity is linked to the presence of Firmicutes, Proteobacteria and Chloroflexi phyla in mesophilic digesters (Greses et al., 2018). However, the microbial structures of microalgae-degrading communities may be different with an added co-substrate and no recent studies have assessed this scenario in a continuous system working at high SRT.

Since anaerobic digestion could be an important step in recycling nutrients for algal cultivation and energy recovery at WWTPs, further research is needed on AD with microalgae and sewage sludge. Although earlier studies have reported on the co-digestion of different raw materials, all were in batch conditions and some were short-term continuous experiments. Few studies have assessed microbial diversity in a co-digestion system, and this would expand our knowledge of the process and identify the

key microbiological members of AD. To the current knowledge of the authors of this manuscript, no studies have evaluated the impact of multiple microalgae species in terms of biogas production in a semi-continuous co-digestion system. The aim of this study was therefore to evaluate the long-term feasibility of semi-continuous ACoD of harvested untreated microalgae in municipal wastewater and primary sludge. The study was carried out in an AnMBR coupled to a biomass reservoir to boost methane production under mesophilic conditions, working at high SRT. This paper reports on the performance of a long-term continuous system with physicochemical and microbial characterization carried out to acquire an in-depth understanding of methane production by raw microalgae and primary sludge ACoD.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Substrates

Microalgae and primary sludge were used as feeding substrates. Primary sludge from the gravity thickener of the Carraixet WWTP (Alboraya, Spain) was sieved through 0.5 mm aperture sieve and diluted to adjust the carbon oxygen demand (COD) concentration to the desired value ($22.8 \text{ g COD} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) to keep the organic loading rate (OLR) in the AnMBR constant. Microalgae were collected from a membrane photobioreactor (MPBR) pilot plant (see González-Camejo et al. (2017) for an extensive description). The algal biomass was concentrated by filtration in an external cross-flow, ultrafiltration hollow-fibre membrane unit (HF 5.0-43-PM500, PURON® Koch Membrane Systems) before being fed to the anaerobic reactor. This unit has a nominal pore size of 500 kDa MWCO (Molecular Weight Cut-Off) and an area of 2.1 m^2 . Filtration was carried out to increase the COD concentration from 0.5 to 9.6 g

COD·L⁻¹ on average and so achieve the desired OLR value. Both substrates were physicochemically characterized and stored at 4 °C for a maximum of 3 weeks.

2.2. Experimental set-up

The experimental set-up for the continuous anaerobic digestion trials consisted of two cylindrical methacrylate continuously stirred tank reactors with a total volume of 14 L and a working volume of 9 L (Figure 1). The reactor 1 (AnMBR) was connected to an external hollow-fibre ultrafiltration membrane (UHF) module (PURON Koch membrane systems, 0.03 µm pore size) with a surface area of 0.42 m², a total volume of 1 L and a working volume of 0.9 L. Sludge was kept homogenized by continuous recirculation through the UHF, where the effluent was obtained by vacuum filtration. The membrane was programmed to operate in three different stages: filtration, backwash and relaxation. A basic filtration-relaxation cycle was performed once per day in order to obtain enough permeate to maintain the desired hydraulic retention time (HRT), and relaxation state was performed during the rest of the day. Transmembrane pressure (TMP) was monitored and recorded to evaluate membrane performance.

The purge stream from the AnMBR was fed to the reactor 2 (AnR), which acted as a biomass reservoir and had the same characteristics as reactor 1 but lacked a membrane (Figure 1).

Three biogas blowers were connected in order to allow mixing of both reactors and the membrane module and to control biofilm formation on the membrane. One blower recycled a fraction of the biogas produced in the AnMBR reactor from top to bottom, while another recycled the remaining biogas fraction from the top of the reactor to the bottom of the UHF. The biogas produced in the AnR was recycled from top to bottom of the digester. An MGC 10 milligas counter (Ritter) was used to measure daily

volumetric biogas production. Gas volumes were normalized to standard conditions (1 atm, 0 °C).

The system was sealed to avoid gas leakage and was equipped with pH, redox and temperature electrodes. Headspace pressure was also measured in both reactors. A data acquisition program was used to continuously monitor the process.

2.3. Operating conditions

Anaerobic digestion was performed during 440 days under mesophilic conditions. Both reactors were kept at 35 °C by a water jacket connected to a thermostatic water bath.

Reactor 1 was inoculated with sludge from a lab-scale mesophilic reactor digesting microalgae biomass. Reactor 1 was operated at an OLR of $0.52 \text{ g COD}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$, a SRT of 100 d and at a HRT of 30 d. These values were based on the results of a previous study evaluating SRT impact on microalgae biodegradability (Giménez et al., 2017).

Reactor 2 was filled with the daily purge from the AnMBR and was operated at an OLR of $0.15 \text{ g COD}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$. As the biomass was not recirculated, SRT and HRT were set at 100 days. Reactor 2 thus offers a biomass reservoir and a two-stage system providing a total SRT of 200 d (100 d in the AnMBR plus 100 d in the AnR). The AnMBR was fed with the primary sludge and microalgae mixture in a mass proportion of 62-38% (based on volatile solids content). This ratio was chosen according to the results of a co-digestion pilot plant simulation (using DESSAS® software) to reproduce the mass proportion produced in a WWTP combining an AnMBR treating settled wastewater followed by an MPBR as a secondary treatment (Seco et al., 2018).

2.4. Analytical methods

Volatile Solids (VS), Total Solids (TS), VFA and Alkalinity (Alk) were measured in duplicate three times per week. Other parameters such as Total and Soluble COD (T-

COD and S-COD, respectively), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Volatile Suspended Solids (VSS), Total Nitrogen (T-N), Ammonium (NH₄-N), Total Phosphorus (T-P), Phosphate (PO₄-P), and Sulphate (SO₄-S) were determined once a week, also in duplicate. All the analyses were performed according to Standard Methods (APHA, 2012).

Biogas samples from the reactor headspace were collected three times a week and methane content was analysed by a Gas Chromatograph fitted with a Flame Ionization Detector (CG-FID, Agilent Technologies), equipped with a thermal conductivity detector and a TRACER column (Teknokroma): 15 m × 0.53 mm × 1 μm. The temperatures of the column and the detector were maintained at 40 °C and 250 °C, respectively. The carrier gas was helium and the flow rate was constant at 5 mL·min⁻¹. The sample gas concentration was compared to a standard pure methane gas (99.99%; Air Products Inc.).

The composition of microalgae and primary sludge was analysed by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) by searching for the presence of the following elements: C, N, H, and S by means of an XL-30 ESEM (Philips, Netherlands). Substrate samples were attached to the Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) stub using silver lacquer. The SEM stub with the sample was then introduced into the XL-30 and the pressure was reduced to 10⁻⁵ bar, after which the sample surface was visualised and an area was selected for microanalysis. The spot-size value was modified until a Dead Time of around 30% was achieved.

2.5. Biodegradability rate, biomethane potential, methane yield and ammonia concentration calculations.

The anaerobic process efficiency was evaluated in terms of biodegradability percentage, biomethane potential percentage, methane yield and ammonia concentration using the following equations.

$$\% \text{ Biodegradability} = \frac{CH_4 \sim COD + H_2S \sim COD}{COD_{influent}} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\% \text{ Biomethane potential} = \frac{CH_4 \sim COD}{COD_{influent}} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$Y^{CH_4} = \frac{CH_4 \sim V}{COD_{influent}} ; \frac{L CH_4}{g COD} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

$$[NH_3] = \frac{TAN}{1 + \frac{10^{-pH}}{10^{-(0.09018 + \frac{2728.92}{T})}}} ; \frac{mg}{L} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where $COD_{influent}$ ($g \text{ COD} \cdot d^{-1}$) is the COD of the influent; $CH_4 \sim COD$ is the COD of the produced methane (biogas methane and methane dissolved in the effluent) ($g \text{ COD} \cdot d^{-1}$); $H_2S \sim COD$ is the COD consumed by sulphate reducing bacteria (SRB) for sulphate reduction ($g \text{ COD} \cdot d^{-1}$), TAN is the total ammonia nitrogen in the reactor ($mg \cdot L^{-1}$), T is the temperature expressed in Kelvin and $CH_4 \sim V$ is the volume of methane produced (biogas methane plus dissolved methane in the effluent) at 1 atm and 0 °C (L).

2.6. Microbial population analysis

Inoculum and digestate samples were pelleted after centrifuging 1 mL of sludge at 4000 x g and stored at -20°C until nucleic acid extraction procedures. Besides the inoculum, three samples were collected from the AnMBR and AnR after 286, 323 and 400 days of operation. All these samples correspond to the pseudo-steady period determined when COD, TS and biogas production showed no variation for 154 d and were therefore considered biological replicates. A negative control with sterilized and nuclease-free

deionized water was also included at the beginning of the DNA extraction procedure. Following the protocol described by Zamorano-López et al. (2019) the nucleic acid material was extracted from all the samples and used for 16S rRNA amplicon sequencing. Libraries targeting the v3-4 region were sequenced in an Illumina MiSeq in a 2x300 bp paired-end run (Illumina, USA). The resulting raw sequences were deposited on the NCBI SRA depository under Bioproject PRJNA434206 (biosamples SAMN11567546, SAMN11567547, SAMN11567548 from AnMBR; SAMN11567570, SAMN11567571 and SAMN11567572 from AnR; besides inoculum SAMN11567595 and negative control SAMN11567565).

Downstream amplicon sequencing analysis was performed according to a previous study (Zamorano-López et al. 2019) in Quantitative Insights into Microbial Ecology (QIIME) pipelines and R-Studio software plus *vegan* and *mixOmics* packages. The resulting filtered sequences were clustered into Operational Taxonomic Units defined at 3% dissimilarity (OTU_{0.97}). Alpha diversity analysis was performed through a Simpson Evenness Estimator and the number of observed OTU_{0.97}. Beta-diversity analysis through principal co-ordinate analysis (PCoA) of the weighted unifrac distance matrix was performed to explore the microbial community structure changes between the inoculum, the pseudo-steady AnMBR and AnR samples, as well as the negative control.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Source characterization

Harvested raw microalgae and primary sludge were used as feeding substrates during ACoD. The average characteristics of feedstock are shown in Table 1. Since an optimized C/N ratio is important for substrate degradation (Yen and Brune, 2007), the elemental composition of both feeding substrates was also determined. Microalgae

composition (47.69% C, 9.27% N, 0.61% S, 7.41% H) led to a low C/N ratio of 5.15, as expected, due to its high protein content. Nevertheless, primary sludge composition (40.01% C, 4.42% N, 1.47% S, 6.23% H) also resulted in a low (9.06) C/N ratio. The C/N ratio for the feeding mixture was not that recommended for an anaerobic digestion process, according to previous studies (Sialve et al., 2009; Yen and Brune, 2007).

Microscopic examination showed that from Days 1 to 60, wastewater microalgae were mainly composed of *Scenedesmus* spp. (>99% of the total eukaryotic cells); from Days 61 to 210, the culture was dominated by *Scenedesmus* spp. and *Chlorella* spp. in different proportions, and from Day 211 to the end of the period, the culture was dominated by *Chlorella* spp. This shift in microalgae species will be discussed in Section 3.2.

3.2. Anaerobic co-digestion

The harvested microalgae and primary sludge were co-digested under mesophilic conditions in two interconnected anaerobic digesters. Biological process performance was evaluated by monitoring different parameters such as methane production, TS, VS and nutrients concentrations in both reactors (see Figure 2). As seen in Figure 2b, from Days 71 to 120 biogas production dropped drastically in the AnMBR due to an operating problem related with a gas leakage. After this was solved, methane production rose again and the system rapidly recovered stability. The pseudo-steady state of the sludge and permeate effluents was achieved after 286 days, as seen by TS evolution (Figure 2a) and methane production (Figure 2b) and was maintained for 154 days. Table 2 gives the results obtained in each reactor in the pseudo-steady state. During the last 154 d, the cumulative average biogas production from the system was $1.94 \text{ L}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$, where $1.87 \text{ L}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$ of this biogas (96.4%) was produced from the AnMBR and the rest ($0.07 \text{ L}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$

¹) from the AnR. Weekly methane production was therefore much higher in the AnMBR reactor (Figure 2b), as expected, since most of the degradation of the feeding substrates occurs in the AnMBR. However, the biogas methane content was similar in both reactors, around 68% (Figure 2b), suggesting the presence of an efficient methanogenic population in both AnMBR and AnR. This will be discussed later in the microbial analysis in Section 3.3.

The mesophilic AnMBR reached a methane yield of 256 mL CH₄·g COD_{inf}⁻¹ (435 mL CH₄·g SV_{inf}⁻¹) due to the high hydrolytic activity of the system, which corresponds to an average biomethane potential of 72%. Total biodegradability achieved in the system was around 73%, being only 1% of the total biodegradable COD consumed by sulphate-reducing bacteria. As previous batch assays had shown that primary sludge mono-digestion yielded 64% biodegradability (data not shown), the biodegradability increase up to 73% is related to the synergetic effect of co-digesting primary sludge and microalgae in the AnMBR. This value is also higher than the findings of previous studies on microalgae digestion. A biodegradability of 9.4% was achieved in a CSTR for untreated *Scenedesmus* spp. (González-Fernández et al., 2013). Greses et al. (2018) reported a methane yield of 35.7 mL CH₄·g COD_{inf}⁻¹ (11.9% of biodegradability) when digesting *Scenedesmus* microalgae in a CSTR operating at an SRT of 50 days, but a yield of 148.5 mL CH₄·g COD_{inf}⁻¹ when digesting *Scenedesmus* microalgae in an AnMBR system operating at an SRT of 70 days. Passos et al. (2014) reported 120 mL CH₄·g COD_{inf}⁻¹ when digesting *Scenedesmus* and *Chlorella* grown in high rate ponds for wastewater treatment and also observed that methane yield was enhanced by 42% with microwave treatment (170 mL CH₄·g COD_{inf}⁻¹). Although different pretreatments have been studied for microalgae digestion and have shown positive effects on the methane production rate, these treatments are normally costly processes and also have

some drawbacks that need to be considered, such as the formation of recalcitrant compounds that could potentially harm the process performance (Mendez et al., 2013). Furthermore, the methane rates achieved in several pretreated microalgae digestion experiments (Magdalena et al., 2018) were lower than the $435 \text{ mL CH}_4 \cdot \text{g SV}_{\text{inf}}^{-1}$ value observed in the present study, demonstrating that ACoD with primary sludge can substantially improve microalgae mono-digestion and increase the methane yield without requiring costly pretreatments. The mix of both substrates accelerated the AD process, as already reported in other studies: Solé-Bundó et al. (2018) observed a threefold increase in methane yield when co-digesting microalgae and primary sludge, compared to pretreated microalgae mono-digestion. The authors reported that the higher the proportion of primary sludge, the higher the methane rate, obtaining the highest methane yield ($460 \text{ mL CH}_4 \cdot \text{g VS}^{-1}$) when adding 75% of primary sludge to pretreated microalgae. This is a little higher than the value observed in the present work, which could be explained by the use of pretreated algae and a higher proportion of primary sludge in Solé-Bundó et al. (2018). The higher the proportion of primary sludge in the AnMBR co-digester the better the result that can be expected. The ACoD proposed here should thus be considered as a less costly strategy for achieving high bioenergy recovery ratios from raw microalgae, since no algae pretreatment was required.

This enhanced methane production could theoretically be explained by an optimised C/N ratio due to the addition of primary sludge. As the low C/N ratio of algal sludge is regarded as an important limiting factor to anaerobic digestion, adding primary sludge was expected to improve the C/N ratio to 20-25 (Yen and Brune 2007). As mentioned in Section 3.1, a C/N ratio of 5.15 for microalgae and 9.06 for primary sludge was found in the substrates used in this work, but these values were apparently not suitable for anaerobic digestion (Yen and Brune, 2007); however, high biodegradability was

achieved in the present work. Primary sludge, mainly formed by colloidal organic matter, is easier to biodegrade and co-digesting it with microalgae seems to have synergy positive effects on substrate biodegradability, as reported by Olsson et al. (2014), who found 23% more methane production when co-digesting sewage sludge with microalgae (63/37% based in VS content) in batch tests. Accordingly, the present results suggest that the presence of primary sludge promoted an efficient microbial community for microalgae degradation, in which syntrophic pathways probably played an important role in degrading the substrate first into intermediate products and later into methane, as will be further discussed in Section 3.3.

The mesophilic AnR reached an average biodegradability percentage of 10.2%, which corresponds to a methane yield of $35 \text{ mL CH}_4 \cdot \text{g COD}_{\text{inf}}^{-1}$, so that the second reactor enabled a 5% improvement in the total methane rate while the system achieved an overall 78% biodegradability percentage.

Regarding microalgae composition, previous studies have reported a dependence on microalgae species for biogas production. In the present study a shift of microalgae species from *Scenedesmus* to *Chlorella* was assessed before achieving a pseudo-steady state: up to Day 210 the culture was dominated entirely by *Scenedesmus* or both *Scenedesmus* and *Chlorella* and from Day 211 to the end of the period it was dominated by *Chlorella* spp. (see Section 3.1). Although several studies (Frigon et al., 2013; Mussgnug et al., 2010) have reported a difference in *Chlorella* or *Scenedesmus* anaerobic biodegradability, no differences in terms of biogas production (Figure 2b) were found. Several factors, such as culture medium and growth conditions, could have had a significant impact on the specific methane yield. Moreover, the other studies (Frigon et al., 2013; Mussgnug et al., 2010) focused on microalgae mono-digestion. Then, no differences in methane yield were found when co-digesting wastewater-grown

Chlorella or *Scenedesmus* with primary sludge in an AnMBR, which proved to be a resilient system that would have advantages if the process were to be scaled up.

Process stability in the reactor was evaluated during the whole period by means of pH, VFA, nutrient concentrations and alkalinity. pH evolution was continuously monitored and showed values in the range of 6.8-7.1, so that no pH adjustment was required. VFA did not accumulate in the effluent due to the high alkalinity (Table 2) during the whole period. In spite of the high VFA concentrations in the digester influent stream (Table 1), due to the high VFA concentration in the primary sludge, the average ratio VFA alkalinity / total alkalinity was kept around 0.01. This value is lower than that reported in the literature (0.4) for the process to function well and avoids methanogenic reaction being the rate-limiting step (Marti et al., 2008). Total alkalinity should be above 2 g $\text{CaCO}_3 \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ to maintain a stable process. In both digesters the total alkalinity was higher than 2 (Table 2) indicating stable conditions.

With regard to nutrient concentrations in the AnMBR effluent stream, around 400 mg $\text{NH}_4\text{-N} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ (Figure 2c) and 29 mg $\text{PO}_4\text{-P} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$ were released from the algae and sludge ACoD. As a result of the mineralization process, the effluent ammonium concentration was higher than the feeding stream concentration. However, the phosphate concentration was lower (Table 1). The fact that the free ammonia concentration (Table 2) remained below the typical inhibition concentrations (80 mg L^{-1}) reported in other studies (Garcia et al., 2009) should be noted. The nutrient-rich permeate obtained through microalgae and primary sludge ACoD could be recycled for different purposes, such as algae cultivation in WWTPs (Viruela et al., 2016) or to replace inorganic fertilizers (Zamalloa et al., 2012b). For instance, ammonium could be recovered as ammonium sulphate using ion exchange with zeolites, absorption-desorption or synthetic resins or membrane contactors. Seco et al. (2018) reported an 83% ammonium

recovery efficiency in the form of ammonium sulphate while using membrane contactors. Regarding phosphate concentration, the low values observed in the effluent ($29 \text{ mg PO}_4\text{-P}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) suggest that a chemical precipitation took place in the reactor and that phosphorus mineralization should be considered and further evaluated (data not shown). Martí et al., (2017) identified the anaerobic digester as a “hot spot” of uncontrolled P precipitation and proposed some alternatives, such as an elutriation step before the AD. Then, research should be addressed to avoid uncontrolled precipitation in this system. Besides that, the digestate had high total nitrogen and phosphorus contents ($860 \text{ mg N}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and $151 \text{ mg P}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ respectively). These nutrient concentrations in the biosolids fraction suggest it could be used in agriculture, as applying biosolids to land has now become popular due to their potential for recycling valuable components such as organic matter, N, P, and other plant nutrients, especially for soils deficient in organic matter (Sharma et al., 2017). In this regard, the present results appear to be a promising strategy for benefitting from the nutrient-rich permeate and biosolids generated in the AnMBR during bioenergy production. It is noteworthy that the AnR digestate also presented a high nutrient concentration, as can be seen in Table 2 (around $500 \text{ mg NH}_4\text{-N}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and $18 \text{ mg PO}_4\text{-P}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$).

The anaerobic co-digestion of raw microalgae and primary sludge under mesophilic conditions in an AnMBR thus gave higher methane yields than microalgae or primary sludge mono-digestion. Disruption of the *Scenedesmus* and *Chlorella* cell-wall was achieved without any pre-treatment and no differences were found in the performance of both species of microalgae digestion, offering a robust system for future full-scale implementation. Wastewater-grown microalgae cannot be widely considered as the main feedstock for full-scale applications because of their low substrate availability and their being difficult to biodegrade without pre-treatment. On the other hand, large

amounts of primary sludge are easily available from wastewater treatment plants, although it does need further treatment. In this context, co-digesting this sludge with microalgae is a promising approach for future water resource recovery facilities (WRRF).

3.3. Microbial population analysis during microalgae and primary sludge anaerobic co-digestion

16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing revealed the different compositions of the inoculum and digestate AnMBR samples. Since the AnR was kept as a biomass reservoir during the whole experimental period, the microbial community was also evaluated in this reactor. The aim was to discover the effect of doubling total SRT (200 d) in the system on the microbial population and explore the stability of the microbial community detected in the AnMBR. The beta-diversity analysis of the samples (Figure 3a), including the negative control, revealed that the community structure had shifted during the ACoD. Similar diversity was found in both the AnMBR and AnR with minor differences in the evenness of some groups. The Simpson Evenness Index was higher in the AnMBR than AnR samples (0.019 vs. 0.016). The higher number of species in the AnMBR than in the ANR (3852 vs. 2831 OTU_{0.97}) could be due to the presence of an ultrafiltration membrane in the AnMBR, which has been reported to increase microbial community diversity in terms of species richness (Greses et al., 2018). The higher diversity could also be explained by the intrinsic microbial diversity of both the microalgae and primary sludge substrates fed to the AnMBR. Accordingly, the species diversity and evenness in the AnR would more accurately reveal the steady community structure of the system, since the AnR's SRT was assumed to be twice that of the AnMBR (200 d).

Figure 3b shows the changes in OTU_{0.97} composition identified in the system performance. Different members of Chloroflexi, Proteobacteria, Caldisei, Firmicutes, Cloacimonetes, Bacteroidetes, Thermotoga and Synergistetes phyla (Bacteria domain) were enhanced during ACoD of microalgae and primary sludge. Among them, Chloroflexi and Proteobacteria were the most abundant, with relative abundances of 17.6% (AnMBR), 18.2% (AnR) and 20.6% (AnMBR), 15.9% (AnR), correspondingly (Table 3). Methanogens were established in the system, as revealed by the presence of the Euryarchaeota phylum (Archaea domain).

The degradation of both co-substrates resulted in a dominance of potential saccharolytic Anaerolineaceae members (phylum Chloroflexi). The inoculum and both reactors shared an OTU_{0.97} related to this family, although changes in its relative abundance were detected. The Anaerolineaceae percentage decreased from 14.9% in the inoculum to 6.5% and 7.1% in the AnMBR and the AnR, respectively. The remarkable dominance of this OTU_{0.97} in the inoculum is related to its previous acclimation to microalgae degradation. Anaerolineaceae are widely reported in mesophilic anaerobic systems and have been likewise detected in recent studies exploring microbial communities during microalgae degradation (Gonzalez-Fernandez et al., 2018; Greses et al., 2018).

However, the addition of an extra substrate like primary sludge promoted different groups in the system, yielding a different community in terms of relative abundance distribution. The presence of Anaerolineaceae members in both AnMBR and AnR suggests their importance during saccharolytic fermentation from microalgae and primary sludge.

Hydrolytic microorganisms from other phyla were observed in both reactors besides Chloroflexi saccharolytic fermenters. Members of Thermotogae, a bacterial group capable of sustaining growth over a remarkably wide range of temperature and various

simple sugars (e.g., glucose) and complex polysaccharides (e.g., xylan and starch) (De Vos et al., 2009), were observed. Thermotogae includes a mesophilic genus, *Mesotoga*, which has been suggested to be a relevant member during AD of sludge (Lee et al., 2018). The OTU_{0.97} related to *Mesotoga* was detected around 1.6% relative abundance values in both AnMBR and AnR. This *Mesotoga* could be involved in sugar oxidizing processes, including cellobiose and xylose, to produce acetate, sulphide and carbon dioxide, as reported in Lee et al. (2018). Another member of this phylum was found in the present work (*Defluviitoga* genus) at values around 2.6% in both AnMBR and AnR. *Defluviitoga* are able to degrade a large diversity of monosaccharides, disaccharides and polysaccharides, including cellulose and xylan, leading to acetate, ethanol and propionate production (Maus et al., 2016). Finally, members of phylum Bacteroidetes (family Lentimicrobiaceae) were found at a relative abundance of 1.2% and 1.0% in the AnMBR and AnR, respectively. Lentimicrobiaceae contains a strictly anaerobic mesophilic bacteria able to degrade complex polysaccharides such as starch. All the groups mentioned in this paragraph could play an important role in microalgae ACoD, since similar studies have reported the presence of cellulose in both microalgae and primary sludge (Solé-Bundó et al., 2019).

A remarkable presence of *Smithella* (Deltaproteobacteria) was detected during pseudo-steady state conditions in the AnMBR (11.6%) and the AnR (5.6%). This genus was also observed in the inoculum but at a lower abundance (5.5%). *Smithella* is involved in the conversion of propionate into acetate, a syntrophic pathway known as the “*Smithella*-pathway” (Leng et al., 2018). This metabolic process can enhance methane production in anaerobic co-digestion as it provides acetate to methanogens. Indeed, together with *Smithella*, the acetoclastic methanogen *Methanosaeta* was observed in both tanks at similar relative abundance values of 3.1% and 3.6% (AnMBR and AnR,

respectively). Both microorganisms have been described as common syntrophic partners during methane production and identified as active members of full-scale anaerobic digesters (Mei et al., 2016). The presence of *Smithella* and *Methanosaeta* thus explains the production of methane-enriched biogas (68.4% and 67.3% content in the AnMBR and AnR systems, respectively) during microalgae and primary sludge co-digestion. This syntrophic relationship suggests the importance of the synergy obtained by adding an extra carbon source during microalgae co-digestion, such as primary sludge.

Another dominant OTU_{0.97} detected was assigned to *Caldisericum* (phylum Caldiserica). This genus belongs to a poorly described phylum, although recent studies have also detected it in systems with high solids retention time such as the Up-flow Anaerobic Sludge Bed (UASB) reactors (Chen et al., 2017). This suggests that the role of *Caldisericum* in microalgae and primary sludge ACoD could be related to the high SRT in the reactor. However, further research with complementary approaches to 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing, such as proteomics (Heyer et al., 2015) is needed to elucidate its metabolic implications during microalgae co-digestion.

Regarding proteolytic microorganisms, members of Synergistaceae family (phylum Synergistes) reached high relative abundance in the AnMBR (4.4%) and even higher values in the AnR (7.5%). Although no taxonomic assignment below family level was obtained after OTU_{0.97} clustering, the role of this group in releasing acetate, propionate and butyrate from peptides is commonly known (Jumas-Bilak et al., 2014). Thus, Synergistaceae are suggested as relevant donors of methanogenic substrates in the present study. Another OTU_{0.97} detected was *Coprothermobacter* (phylum Firmicutes), which is more abundant in thermophilic anaerobic digesters but it has been also isolated from mesophilic systems treating protein-rich wastewater (Etchebehere et al., 1998),

indicating that they can tolerate lower temperatures. The high protein content of microalgae (around 60% (Sialve et al., 2009)) could explain the growth of this genus in the system. Moreover, *Candidatus Cloacomonas* genus (phylum Cloacinomicetes) a syntrophic bacterium capable of degrading propionate and amino acids, remained in the system at relative abundances of 3% in the AnMBR and 3.5% in the AnR. Proteolytic microorganisms thus play an important role in the co-digestion system.

Rikenecellaceae (Bacteroidetes phylum), a bacteria group capable of degrading amino acids in syntrophic association with hydrogenotrophic methanogens, reached a relative abundance of 0.7% in the AnMBR and 0.6% in the AnR. The release of hydrogen into the system can promote syntrophic-acetate oxidation, enhancing methane production as a result of the higher acetate release in the reactor. According to Leng et al. (2018), the maintenance of a good flux of hydrogen release and consumption during fermentation and hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis can facilitate the production of acetate, which can then be reduced to methane. Hence, the presence of these hydrogen-producing amino acid fermenters related to Bacteroidetes could positively influence microalgae co-digestion, despite their low relative abundances. However, further research considering microbial absolute abundance measurements, with reliance on their activity levels based on RNA-sequencing, besides tracking their metabolism implications (through innovative approaches like proteomics and protein-stable isotope probing) could elucidate the importance of both dominant and minor microbial groups in terms of biogas production.

As shown in Table 2, the free ammonia concentration in both AnMBR and AnR remained at low values, although several proteolytic and amino acid degraders were observed in the system (Synergistaceae, *Coprothermobacter*, *Ca. Cloacomonas* and Rikenecellaceae). No VFA accumulation was observed during pseudo-steady state

period. The results indicate an absence of FAN inhibition, highlighting the favourable effect of adding primary sludge to improve microalgae digestion.

In conclusion, microalgae and primary sludge hydrolysis and fermentation was performed by polysaccharide-degrading bacteria such as Anaerolineaceae, Thermotogae and Lentimicrobiaceae, followed by protein disruption by members of Synergistes phylum besides further fermentation of aminoacids by Rikenecellaceae and *Ca. Cloacomonas*. Syntrophobacterales, mostly composed of syntrophic microorganisms such as *Smithella*, played an important role in microalgae co-digestion, oxidizing key intermediates, such as propionate, providing acetate to methanogens. The presence of methanogens archaea clearly corroborates the anaerobic co-digestion system's performance through methane production.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Anaerobic co-digestion of primary sludge and raw microalgae is a feasible approach for enhancing methane production avoiding costly pre-treatments.

- $130 \text{ mLCH}_4 \cdot \text{d}^{-1} \cdot \text{L}_{\text{reactor}}^{-1}$ were produced at SRT of 100 d in a mesophilic AnMBR, yielding higher biodegradability (73%) than that achieved by microalgae mono-digestion.
- No ammonia inhibition was detected at working conditions ($\sim 5 \text{ mgNH}_3\text{-N} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$).
- An enriched fermentative microbial community was found, being Chloroflexi and Proteobacteria the most abundant phyla.
- Bio-nutrients released from anaerobic co-digestion could be reused for microalgae cultivation or agricultural applications.
- Economic assessment of primary sludge and microalgae co-digestion would be required previous large scale implementation of the technology.

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Table 1: Influent composition (mean \pm standard deviation values).

Parameter	Unit	Microalgae	Sludge
COD	mg COD·L ⁻¹	9739 \pm 187	22818 \pm 296
TSS	mg TSS·L ⁻¹	6242 \pm 340	14574 \pm 623
VFA	mg CH ₃ COOH·L ⁻¹	103 \pm 68	1126 \pm 54
Alk	mg CaCO ₃ ·L ⁻¹	310 \pm 96	316 \pm 157
T-N	mg N·L ⁻¹	480 \pm 85	382 \pm 189
NH ₄ -N	mg N·L ⁻¹	33 \pm 15	111 \pm 35
PO ₄ -P	mg P·L ⁻¹	4.4 \pm 3.4	66 \pm 11
T-P	mg P·L ⁻¹	81 \pm 15	175 \pm 21
SO ₄ -S	mg S·L ⁻¹	92 \pm 53	22 \pm 14

COD: Carbon Oxygen Demand; TSS: Total Suspended Solids; VFA: Volatile Fatty Acids; Alk: Alkalinity; TN: Total Nitrogen; TP: Total Phosphorus

Table 2. Methane production, effluent characterization and removal efficiency from microalgae co-digestion with primary sludge in both reactors (Mean values standard \pm deviation). nd: not detected.

	AnMBR	AnR
Methane yield (mL CH ₄ ·g COD _{inf} ⁻¹)	256 \pm 10	35 \pm 10
CH ₄ in biogas (%)	68.4 \pm 2.5	67.5 \pm 2.7
pH	6.9 \pm 0.3	7.2 \pm 0.1
VFA (mg CH ₃ COOH·L ⁻¹)	nd	nd
ALK (mg CaCO ₃ ·L ⁻¹)	2030 \pm 123	2050 \pm 115
TP (mg P·L ⁻¹)	148 \pm 19	70 \pm 11
PO ₄ -P (mg P·L ⁻¹)	28.6 \pm 2.2	18.3 \pm 0.9
TN (mg N·L ⁻¹)	857 \pm 176	710 \pm 96
NH ₄ -N (mg N·L ⁻¹)	401 \pm 42	503 \pm 18
NH ₃ -N (mg N·L ⁻¹)	5.15 \pm 2.7	12.5 \pm 2.5
Biodegradation (%)	73.1 \pm 2.6	10.2 \pm 2.2
VS removal (%)	70.0 \pm 3.3	10.2 \pm 3.6
COD removal (%)	70.8 \pm 3.4	13.2 \pm 2.5

VFA: Volatile Fatty Acids; Alk: Alkalinity; TP: Total Phosphorus; TN: Total Nitrogen; VS: Volatile Solids; COD: Carbon Oxygen Demand

Table 3. Mean and standard deviation values of the dominant OTU_{0.97} found in the AnMBR and in the AnR (n=3) plus the composition of the inoculum sample analysed by 16S rRNA gene sequencing.

Taxonomy assignment	Inoculum	AnMBR	AnR
	m	R	
Below 1% relative abundance groups (summarized)	37.9	35.6±1.3	35.1±1.7
d. Bacteria; p. Proteobacteria; c. Deltaproteobacteria; o. Syntrophobacterales; f. Syntrophaceae; g. <i>Smithella</i>	5.5	11.6±1.6	5.6±0.5
d. Bacteria; p. Chloroflexi; c. Anaerolineae; o. Anaerolineales; f. Anaerolineaceae	14.9	6.5±0.5	7.1±0.3
d. Bacteria; p. Caldiserica; c. Caldisericia; o. Caldisericales; f. Caldiseriaceae; g. <i>Caldisericum</i>	0.0	6.5±1.0	5.8±1.8
d. Bacteria; p. Chloroflexi; c. Anaerolineae; o. Anaerolineales; f. Anaerolineaceae; uncultured genus	4.9	6.3±0.7	5.8±1.0
d. Bacteria; p. Synergistetes; c. Synergistia; o. Synergistales; f. Synergistaceae; uncultured genus	0.53	4.4±0.6	7.5±1.3
d. Bacteria; p. Firmicutes; c. Clostridia; o. Thermoanaerobacterales; f. Thermodesulfobiaceae; g. <i>Coprothermobacter</i>	n.d	3.2±2.0	5.8±1.7
d. Archaea; p. Euryarchaeota; c. Methanomicrobia; o. Methanosarcinales; f. Methanosaetaceae; g. <i>Methanosaeta</i>	0.4	3.1±0.3	3.6±0.3
d. Bacteria; p. Thermotogae; c. Thermotogae; o. Petrotogales; f. Petrotogaceae; g. <i>Defluviitoga</i>	n.d	2.6±0.7	2.7±0.8
d. Bacteria; p. Chloroflexi; SBR2076 group	1.4	2.6±0.1	2.9±0.4
d. Bacteria; p. Cloacimonetes; Candidatus <i>Cloacamonas</i>	4.4	2.0±0.5	2.2±0.3
d. Bacteria; p. Thermotogae; c. Thermotogae; o. Kosmotogales; f. Kosmotogaceae; g. <i>Mesotoga</i>	0.2	1.5±0.1	1.6±0.1
d. Bacteria; p. Bacteroidetes; c. Sphingobacteriia; o. Sphingobacteriales; f. Lentimicrobiaceae; uncultured genus	1.0	1.2±0.2	1.0±0.2
d. Bacteria; p. Bacteroidetes; c. Bacteroidia; o. Bacteroidales; f. Rikenellaceae; S50 wastewater-sludge group	0.0	0.7±0.4	0.6±0.3

Non-detected OTU_{0.97} (n.d.). The taxonomic level assigned to each OTU_{0.97} is indicated as follows: phylum (p.), class (c.), order (o.), family (f.) and genus (g.).

Figure 1: Layout of anaerobic co-digestion system showing the anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) and the anaerobic reactor (AnR).

Figure 2. Total Solids (TS) and Volatile Solids (VS) evolution over experimental period in the influent stream and both reactors (a), weekly methane production and % CH₄ in biogas in AnMBR and AnR (b) and ammonium concentration in influent and both reactors (c). Error bars represent the standard deviation of replicate measurements.

Figure 3. a) Principal co-ordinate analysis (PCoA) revealing the microbial structure of the system. Ordination was calculated from the weighted unifracs distance matrix. The two first components were chosen to represent the differences between AnMBR, AnR, inoculum and negative samples analyzed in the 16S rRNA gene amplicon sequencing approach. b) Dominant OTU_{0.97} relative abundances barplots (1% relative abundance threshold). The taxonomic level assigned to each OTU_{0.97} is indicated as follows: phylum (p.), family (f.) and genus (g.).